

DESIGN OF A MECHANICAL JOINT FOR PULTRUDED COMPOSITE RODS

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ABSTRACT

The high axial tensile strength and the low transverse strength of pultruded composite rods present some unique problems in testing with conventional grips. The high transverse compressive forces required in the conventional method of gripping tend to crush the rod, thereby causing premature failure. The present paper presents results from a two-dimensional nonlinear finite element analysis to characterize the contact pressure and stress distributions at the interfaces and maximum axial load available in the jig developed.

INTRODUCTION

The anisotropic and brittle nature of high strength unidirectional pultruded composites make tensile test very difficult because of premature failure with the conventional gripping method [1]. In order to alleviate the load introduction problem the typical tensior and compression specimen has tabs bonded to specimen ends [2].

Design guidelines for end tab grip adapters in tensile testing of pultruded composite rods can be found in ASTM standard D3916-84. These guidelines, however, are not applicable to high strength fiber reinforced composite rods because of slip as a results of higher failure load required.

A new frictional jig was developed by Conoco, Figure 1. In order to determine the ultimate tensile strength, the bolt-clamping forces and resultant contact pressure between the specimen and the tab should be adequate to prevent pull-out of the specimen as well as premature failure at the critical regions.

In the present study, a two-dimensional nonlinear analysis was performed to determine the contact stress distribution around and along the specimen under the tab and also the maximum axial load possible in the jig.

ANALYSIS

In testing circular pultruded rods, the specimen is placed between two cylindrical bushings, called tabs hereafter, and two steel fixtures are bolted together to apply pressure on the specimen as shown in Figure 1. The steel fixtures are joined by several bolts evenly

Presently with Daewoo Heavy Industries, Ltd. Korea.

spaced. The bolts are tightened to a certain preload. During tensile testing, the axial force applied to the steel fixtures is transmitted to the specimen through the friction at the specimen/tab interface.

The friction coefficient of unidirectional graphite/pps composite against smooth steel surface is assumed to be 0.2 [3] in this analysis. It is now desirable to find the bolt tension that must be applied to prevent slip without causing premature failure of the specimen. For the simplicity of analysis problem was divided into two parts as follows:

Around the specimen :

Since the bolt hole size was not an important parameter for the contact stress distribution, it was not included in the analysis. The discrete bolt forces along the outer steel fixture was replaced by a continuous loading. Also, the specimen length was much longer than its diameter, therefore, stress analysis was performed under the assumption of plane strain. The bolts were tightened to apply a compressive pressure (P_a) of, for example, 10 Ksi. Because of the symmetry, only one quarter of the cross section was analyzed, Figure 2.

The stress analysis was performed using the ANSYS finite element code [4]. Three sets of elements were used to model the assembly. Two-dimensional 3-node and 4-node isoparametric elements were used for the solid body. A typical layout of elements and boundary conditions are shown in Figure 2 (180 elements and 180 nodes). At the two different interfaces, double nodes with identical nodal coordinates were used. Two-dimensional nonlinear gap element [4] was applied to connect these two nodes. This element is nonlinear and requires an iterative procedure, with the stiffness matrix reformulated for each iteration, for static convergence. The condition for convergence was the friction force being less than 10 percent different between any successive iterations.

The purpose of this analysis was to delineate the effect of the friction coefficient on the contact pressure and interfacial stress distributions, and to provide information for the design of slip-proof joint.

Fig.1 Tension jig for pultruded composite rod.

Fig.2 Typical cross-section and finite element model.

Along the specimen :

Since the contact pressures at the tab/fixture and tab/specimen interfaces were found to be nearly uniform except at the gaps in the preceding section, the real 3-dimensional problem was simplified to a two-dimensional axisymmetric problem. The modified problem thus consisted of a cylindrical composite rod surrounded by a cylindrical metal tab with a uniform pressure applied at the outer boundary as shown in Figure 3.

In the longitudinal direction, we have used axisymmetric 4-node isoparametric elements. From the symmetry about the mid-plane, only one half of the assembly was considered. Also, the same gap elements as described earlier were used to simulate the interface between the tab and the composite rod.

Fig.3 Finite element model for the analysis of axial loading.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The material properties and geometry data used in the analyses are listed in Table 1. All the results are normalized by either the bolt-clamping pressure or the applied axial stress.

Figure 4 shows the contact pressure distribution at the tab/composite interface. Although there is a significant pressure concentration at the gap, it is interesting to see a nearly uniform pressure distribution over most of the interface.

Equivalent stress [5] contours with a friction coefficient of 0.2 are shown in Figure 5. The maximum value is seen to exist at the junction as expected. Therefore, the bolt pressure should be adjusted so as not to cause premature failure at this point. The calculated stresses were used in the Tsai-Hill failure criterion [6] to determine the maximum bolt pressure that could be applied without failure of the composite rod. It was found that there was no failure in the specimen until the bolt pressure was increased to 11 ksi.

Under the bolt pressure of 10 ksi, the specimen is expected to be pulled out when an axial stress of 200 ksi, which is about the failure strength of the specimen, is applied. From additional computer run, it was found that the specimen pull-out could be prevented by increasing the bolt pressure about 5 percent. Under the increased bolt pressure, the slip area was about 86 percent of the total contact area.

The axial stresses distribution near the interface, normalized by the applied axial stress, are shown in Figure 6. When there is little slip between the specimen and the tab, stress concentration can be as high as 125 percent at the end of tab. As the applied axial load increases, the slip area increases, and the stress concentration decreases and finally disappears. Therefore, the stress concentration will not cause premature failure during tensile testing.

Another interesting point is that as slip propagates inward, a large portion of the specimen under the tab becomes effective in supporting the axial load, Figure 7. Also, the stress concentration at the tab end is substantially reduced.

Table 1. Material property and geometry data used.

Fixture & Bushing :	
Steel	$E_s = 30 \text{ (Msi)}$ $\nu_s = 0.3$
Specimen - Gr/PPS a)	$E_{11} = 17.5 \text{ (Msi)}$ $E_{22} = E_{33} = 1.25 \text{ (Msi)}$ $G_{12} = G_{23} = G_{31} = 0.61 \text{ (Msi)}$ $\nu_{12} = \nu_{23} = \nu_{31} = 0.36$ $X_t = 200 \text{ (ksi)}, X_c = 125 \text{ (ksi)}$ $Y_t = 5.0 \text{ (ksi)}, Y_c = 20 \text{ (ksi)}$ $S_t = 10 \text{ (ksi)}$
Geometry data -	Specimen diameter = 0.25 (in) Gap size = 0.01 (in) Tab diameter = 0.375 (in) Tab length = 6 (in)

a) From private communication with manufacturer

Fig.4 Normalized contact pressure distribution at the interface.

Fig.5 Equivalent stress contours in the cross-section of specimen.

CONCLUSIONS

A finite element stress analysis was performed for a tension jig for composite rod. In particular, the effects of friction coefficient and slip on the contact pressure and axial stress distributions was studied. It was found that the contact pressure distribution around the specimen was quite uniform and nearly independent of the friction coefficient. The slip along the tab was found beneficial in relieving the axial stress concentration. These results would be helpful in designing slip-proof mechanical joints for composite rods.

Fig.6 Normalized axial stress distribution near the interface.

Fig.7 Equivalent stress contours for several loading cases.

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